

International Workshop

"Agriculture in Premises of Regional Growth"

Hybrid – online & in-person
 April 26, 2024, Karlsruhe, GERMANY

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i>	08.45-09.15
<i>Regional Growth Through Agriculture: Foundations for Mountain Development</i>	09.15-10.45
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i>	
<i>Agriculture and Education: Key Drivers of Regional Growth in Mountain Communities</i>	10.45-11.00
Q & A	
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Art and Humanity in Mountain Regions</i>	
<i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i>	11.00-11.30
<i>Exploring Art and Humanity in Mountain Regions: Culture, Creativity, and Community</i>	
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i>	11.30-12.00
<i>Art and Humanity in Mountain Regions: Celebrating Culture, Creativity, and Connection</i>	
<i>Session 2 – Agricultural Premises in Education, Social Sciences, and Engineering</i>	
<i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i>	

<p><i>Austria</i></p> <p><i>Agricultural Foundations in Education, Social Sciences, and Engineering</i></p> <p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p>	11.00-11.30
<p><i>Integrating Agriculture with Education, Social Sciences, and Engineering</i></p>	11.30-12.00
<p>Coffee break</p>	12.00-12.15
<p><i>Session 1 – Education, Art and Humanity through Agricultural Lens</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Exploring Education, Art, and Humanity through the Lens of Agriculture</i></p> <p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>Bridging Education, Art, and Humanity: Insights through Agriculture</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p><i>Session 2 – Science and Engineering, Support for Agricultural Development</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Advancing Agricultural Development through Science and Engineering</i></p> <p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p>	12.15-12.45
<p><i>Fostering Agricultural Growth through Science and Engineering Innovation</i></p>	12.45-13.15
<p>Q&A</p>	13.15-13.45
<p>Concluding remarks</p>	13.45-14.00

Location: Karlsruhe Park Arkaden, 1st Floor, Karlsruhe, 76131, Germany